

Exploring the experiences of Autistic Pupils who avail of dual Mainstream and Special Class provision in Irish Primary Schools

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Abstract

This paper explores some current research on the experiences of autistic pupils who avail of dual mainstream and special class provision in Irish primary schools. The focus of this research is on the lived experiences of autistic pupils, whose voices up until now have been excluded from conversations on the appraisal of the national policy for the inclusion of autistic pupils. This research employed qualitative methods using a mosaic approach to empower pupil participation and in doing so further amplifying the voices of autistic pupils from four to twelve years of age. Emerging findings firstly highlight the prevalence of masking among autistic pupils coupled with a realisation by the children that they are different from their neurotypical peers. Secondly the autism classes are seen as being a safe haven by the pupils, who feel understood and enabled to be their full selves in the supportive environment it provides. Finally, there is a striking disconnect between what the pupils' voices and the adult voices each have to say. This highlights a tension between the voices which are the loudest and which are often favoured to advocate on behalf of these children in policy formation and appraisal.

Keywords

Dual provision; autistic pupils; student voice; mosaic approach; masking; social justice; inclusion; neurodiversity

3 Main Highlights

- Dual provision is the response of national policy for the inclusion of autistic pupils for whom neither full-time mainstream or special school provision is currently deemed appropriate.
- Autistic pupils are a heterogeneous group, therefore creative methods are required when researching their experiences and maintaining authenticity in communicating their voices through research.
- Tensions exist when the expectation is that neurodiverse individuals should assimilate to fit neurotypical culture and environments. In this research, the school environment and the culture which is espoused from within are being explored in four primary schools. This research raises some serious implications, namely the importance of accessing the voices of vulnerable participants (i.e. pupils with special educational needs) and in turn using the learnings from ‘research with’ such groups to inform future policy on matters which primarily affect them.

Introduction

Children’s Voices as a Right

The United Nations Convention on the Rights of the Child rules that “states parties shall assure to the child who is capable of forming his or her own views the right to express those views freely in all matters affecting the child, the views of the child being given due weight in accordance with the age and maturity of the child” (United Nations (UN), 1989). However, pupils with special educational needs [SEN] are said to suffer “double denial” of the right to have their voices heard in research about matters which affect them (Lundy, 2007). This is firstly due to their age and secondly due to being assessed as having SEN.

Children's voices have tended to be silenced in decisions about the way their education was provided (Fielding, 2015). Ellsworth (1989) highlights some provocative issues concerning research for social change illuminating key considerations relating to "empowerment", "dialogue" and "critical reflection" when researching with young and vulnerable populations. Neurodivergent individuals or "Exotic others" ought to be humanised and empowered with conscious efforts made to bring their living reality to the fore (Walkerdine, 1985, p.205). A prevailing justification for the involvement of pupils' voices in education is the recognition of their expert role of what it is like to be an autistic pupil with knowledge, insights, experiences and understandings only they can share (Shevlin and Rose, 2008).

Autism viewed through the lens of Neurodiversity

According to the fifth edition of the Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders [DSM-5], Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD) is classified under the following diagnostic criteria; challenges with social communication/interaction, and restricted and repetitive behaviours (American Psychiatric Association [APA], 2013). Persistent 'deficits' in both of these areas must be identified to cause functional impairment which can not be accounted for by general learning delays (APA, 2013). It must be acknowledged that although autism is diagnosed primarily on the basis of social and communicative deficits, neurodiversity demands the recognition and acceptance of the value of cognitive variation as a form of biodiversity. Hence, the understanding and acceptance that autistic individuals do make a positive contribution to society in a socio-ecological perspective which consequently is sought to end discriminatory policies and practices (Chapman, 2020).

A central assertion of the neurodiversity movement is that variations in neurological development and functioning across humans are a natural and valuable part of human variation and therefore are not necessarily pathological (Kapp, 2020). Neurodiversity, as a social justice and civil rights movement, intersects with wider disability rights movements, separating the defect from the individual and owing to the interaction between a non-neurotypical individual and an unaccommodating environment (Hughes, 2016).

Leadbitter, Buckle, Ellis and Dekker (2021) note that the neurodiversity movement demands professionals and researchers to pay due diligence to the Autistic Community and “move away from the normative agenda and attend to the environmental goodness-of-fit, autistic developmental trajectories, internal drivers and experiences, and autistic prioritised intervention targets” (Leadbitter et al., 2021, p.1). This research seeks to engage the voices of a neurodiverse population to explore their experiences of being educated in both a neurotypical classroom and a neurodiverse classroom, which is aimed to facilitate their perceived strengths and needs, concurrently.

International Policy for inclusion

The international community in the form of the United Nations [UN] and its associated treaty bodies and agencies have taken a critical role in establishing a global consensus on inclusion, its principles, and how it should manifest in practice (Byrne, 2020). This is of particular concern given the diverse interpretation of “inclusion” across nations. The United Nations Educational Scientific and Cultural Organisation [UNESCO] report of 2020 entitled “Towards Inclusion and Equity in Education: Status, Trends, and Challenges” provides an educational justification, a social justification, and an economic justification for inclusive education.

Dual Provision/National Policy for the inclusion of autistic pupils

Findings from the NCSE suggest that from 2011-2019, special class provision has risen by 196% in Ireland. In this timeframe, there has also been a 155% increase in the number of students enrolled in special classes (NCSE, 2019). In this same period, overall student numbers have only increased by 7.5%. Currently, almost 80% of all special classes in schools are for autistic pupils (Eurydice, 2019). There is an inherent belief that their needs are greater than the mainstream can accommodate. A further contributing factor to the importance of this research is the dysfunctionality of the current Irish system of support. There has been outcry in recent years due to a lack of places available in special classes and special schools. With a bit of forward planning and reflection on current special class provision from the perspectives of the pupils who avail of it, the system would greatly benefit. Research on the value of special classes until now has included a variety of voices on the issue but on all occasions, the voice of the primary school pupil has been omitted. This research aims to rectify this.

Methods

The conceptual framework used in guiding this research is Flynn's Learner Voice Space framework (2017) (see figure one). Integral to this framework is the acknowledgement of the potential transformative impact of engaging with the voices of learners who are often the subject of research about them. In engaging with these voices, the potential positive impacts on student-teacher relationships and the learner's relationship with their learning environment, further fosters a sense of agency and leadership potential within learners.

TRANSFORMATIVE DIALOGUE

Figure 1. Flynn's (2017) Learner Voice Space Framework

This framework calls for the continued dialogue and involvement of learners in each stage of this research, focusing on the co-construction of knowledge and breaking the barriers of unequal power relations between the researcher and the researched. One of the greatest barriers for researchers working with children is depicting their voices with purity and getting *their* message across as intended, preventing the 'adulteration' of their voices (Flynn, 2013). This framework highlights the ethical and moral imperative for researching with vulnerable participants.

Figure 2. Lundy's (2007) Model of Child Participation

This research is situated in the constructivist paradigm and consisted of a multiple site case study in which qualitative methods were employed. Qualitative methods were most appropriate in addressing the aims of this research, particularly given that this research was driven by participant experiences. Anderson (2010) sees great value in qualitative research as a tool for probing into the nature of educational problems and gaining insights and experiences from those at the epicentre of a phenomenon. Trainor and Graue (2014 p. 269) point to the value of qualitative research in 'engaging the voices of those outside academia, critiquing inequity and using innovative methods to produce new knowledge about persistent educational problems'. Key to this study is the activation of voices from multiple stakeholder groups; particularly, those who have experience of dual-class attendance in primary school.

Sampling

Participants for this research were selected using purposive sampling, guided by clearly defined characteristics (Cohen, Mannion and Morrison, 2017). The deliberate selection of the focus population was guided by the necessity to have a diagnosis of autism and to also have experience of dual provision in a primary school setting. The sample in this study consisted of 15 autistic pupils who were the primary participants (see participant profiling information in table 2 below). Of these three were female. Five of the primary participants had a coexisting diagnosis along with being autistic. These pupils attended four primary schools in the Leinster region and at the time of data collection eight of these pupils were not availing of dual provision due to the ongoing covid-19 pandemic.

Table 1: Primary Participant Profiling Information

Pupil Name	Class Level	Assessed diagnoses	Methods of participation
Ciaran	1st class	Autism	Picture drawing and interview
Cian	1st class	Autism	Picture drawing and interview
Dawn	1st class	Autism	Picture drawing, photovoice, tour and interview
Amy	2nd class	Autism & Speech and Language	Picture drawing and interview
Brian	2nd class	Autism	Picture drawing and interview
Deirdre	2nd class	Autism, Speech and Language and Dyspraxia	Picture drawing, photovoice and interview
Cathal	2nd class	Autism	Picture drawing and interview
Aidan	3rd class	Autism	Picture drawing, scrap book making and interview
Alex	3rd class	Autism & Speech and Language	Picture drawing and interview
Andrew	3rd class	Autism	Picture drawing and interview

Ben	3rd class	Autism, ADHD and Dyslexia	Picture drawing, poster making and interview
Brendan	3rd class	Autism	Picture drawing, poster making and interview
Denis	3rd class	Autism	Picture drawing and interview
Charlie	3rd class	Autism, Dyslexia and on psychiatry medication	Photovoice and interview
Alan	6th class	Autism	Picture drawing and interview

The sample of secondary participants consisted of parents, autism class teachers, mainstream class teachers and special needs assistants who worked with the participating pupils. The voices of the adults were important in this research to further contextualise the pupils' lived experiences. Furthermore, their input facilitated the triangulation of the data captured to represent pupils' lived experiences.

Figure 3. An overview of the relationships between participants

The methods to engage the autistic pupils in this research were informed by a systematic literature review. The review focused on research methods used to elicit the views and experiences of autistic children (4-12 years old) in research between 2004 and 2020. Arising from this review it was concluded that there was no magic bullet or template to apply in this pursuit. While one may assume that involving children with SEN in research is still in its early stages, the heterogeneity inherent in this population perhaps may not be reducible to a predefined template of 'what works'. That said, a number of useful approaches and methods were identified to ease power relations. A common thread in all studies within the review (n=31) was the use of semi-structured interviews which have been used successfully by all researchers in gathering information from participating children. Owing to the neurodiversity of autistic individuals, researchers are encouraged to make some key considerations to reconcile the academic talents which enable such children to cope within the mainstream with the challenges they face. Caution was flagged in attempting to pre-determine a rigid structure for data collection and consequently the use of creative and active methodologies are encouraged along with researcher flexibility (Bradley and Male, 2017).

It was acknowledged that not all children can equally articulate so the idea of there being multiple means of engagement and expression were important (Ware, Ohrt & Swank, 2012). Prominent alternative methods included picture drawing (Peters, Forlin, McInerney and Maclean, 2013), making use of photographs (Zilli, Parsons & Kovshoff, 2020) and making scrapbooks. Such activities centred around the central themes or topics which were pertinent in the research, which are seen to reduce the social anxiety of autistic pupils and to assist in levelling power relations between child and researcher. Offering choice was found to be useful in tipping the balance of power in the direction of the autistic pupils (Brede, Remington, Kenny and Warrington, 2017) along with the use of a 'stop card' (Harrington and

Foster, 2013) similar to the pass card/break card used by Goodall (2018) and movement break cards (Daniel and Billingsley, 2020). Another strategy which was noted involved offering multiple means of representation (Goodall, 2018), all of which were praised by researchers as enabling autistic pupils' participation.

As a result of the findings the mosaic approach (Clark, 2017) was employed, with a choice of methods of participation offered to the autistic pupils. At times the pupils opted to write words rather than draw pictures. Semi-structured interviews were deemed most appropriate as Cohen, Mannion and Morrison state that interviews are "a shared, negotiated and dynamic social moment" (Cohen et al., 2017, p.274) In conducting the research with the autistic pupils, the usefulness of drawings in research has been well documented in studies done by Kendrick and McKay (2004) and Theron et al. (2011). Through drawing, children purposefully bring shape and expression to their experience. McNiff asserts "art then becomes a means through which the child can communicate about those phenomena which are too complex to describe verbally, but which are being perceived and integrated into a child's organisation of reality" (McNiff, 1981, p. 29). A stop card was also utilised.

The research took a flexible, situational approach with the children engaged as agentic participants. On-going assent was sought from participants and member checking was carried out during the analysis of data, further fine tuning the researcher's interpretation of data. Data was also collected with the secondary adult participants through semi-structured interviews.

Preparation for data collection

Preliminary visits were carried out with all pupils prior to data collection. This additional time for building rapport was to serve to maximise the child's comfort with

contributing to the research by becoming familiar with the researcher and completing some preferred tasks (Christensen and James, 2008). These initial visits also allowed for social stories explaining the research to be completed by the researcher where the pupils' assent was sought. The researcher paid three further visits to the pupils in their schools which were for data collection. A pilot study was carried out in advance of data collection to provide the researcher with information on the refinement of her data collection tools. However, during the pilot studies it was found that children welcomed and invited the researcher into their worlds almost immediately.

Ethical Considerations

This research was granted ethical approval from Dublin City University's Special Education Review Committee, where it was subject to full committee review due to the involvement of a particularly vulnerable participant group (DCU, 2020). Parental consent, which was obtained by the signing of hard copy informed consent forms, was followed by the sharing of social stories with their children in preparation for their possible participation in the research. Each participating child was spoken to prior to meeting the researcher and social stories were read to them by their parents to prepare them for their involvement and also to gauge their level of assent. The researcher adopted the principles of the social model of disability, which recognizes that it is the attitudes and structures of society that are disabling and not the participant themselves (Thompson, Cannon and Wickendon, 2020). The dictaphone was acknowledged by the researcher and the participants at the beginning of each interview, again supporting the pupils understanding of the process and checking for their assent and understanding of them being recorded. Data was collected in the pupil's quiet rooms which were attached to the main autism class, an area which was familiar to them and within the confines of the class. The researcher made note of the Designated

Liaison Person in each school on arrival, cognisant that should any child protection issues arise it was known where to go. Following data collection, the aural data on the dictaphone was transcribed verbatim and pseudonyms were applied to the participants during this process to protect participant confidentiality.

Analysis, Results & Discussion

Textual data was analysed using Krippendorff's (2004) eight phase approach to content analysis using the software package NVivo (see figure 4 below). Pictorial data which includes the children's drawings and photographs were analysed semiotically using Agnieszka-Duncan's 4-SASA (Agnieszka-Duncan, 2013). See appendix 1. The emerging findings are rooted in the pupils' voices and drawings as the pupils were the primary participants, and further contextualised through the voices of the adult participants whose voices were secondary in this research.

Figure 4: An outline of Content Analysis by Krippendorff (2004)

Emerging themes and subthemes

Four main themes and numerous sub-themes emerged from the autistic pupils in this research. A fifth theme explores these themes in light of adult participant responses. For the purpose of this paper, due to constraints on word count, only two of these pupil themes will be elaborated upon. These included 1) an awareness of difference and 2) emotional well-being. The third theme centres around the adult perspectives of both of these areas. These themes will be briefly explored below.

Theme One: Awareness of Difference

Pupils demonstrated a strong awareness that they were different from their neurotypical peers. This awareness stems from two key points 1) the pupils have a

perception of being different, and 2) the pupils express a perception of what this difference looks like.

Six of the fifteen participating pupils used the ‘autism’ label and linked it with themselves specifically, briefly demonstrating an understanding of what this might have meant. For example, one child shared “I’ve autism” as he assured the researcher that he knew why she was working with him (Alan, 6th class). Two pupils drew the link with the special class and autism, explaining “in the autism class, all the, well all the kids are autism” (Brendan, 3rd class). Ciaran further elaborated on his emerging understanding of what autism is, explaining “so I have autism...and yeah you know what autism is, it means your brain functions different to others...I think it means I can hear something different” (Ciaran, 1st class). Alan compared autistic individuals to neurotypical individuals by relating the different paces at which different people “learn the world at”. He claimed “some people without autism can learn the world quicker than people with autism” (Alan, 6th class). These different levels of understanding are dominated by an understanding of their identity around their placement in the autism class, with lots of figuring out to be done to determine what autism means.

Theme Two: Emotional well-being

This theme focuses on the emotional experiences of the autistic pupils in light of their dual educational environments. There is an awareness that the learning environment is incongruent with their strengths and needs. This theme brings into sharp focus the aspects of these environments, which are supportive and not supportive of autistic pupils’ well-being and learning in school.

Pupils spoke of some of the challenges school poses for them, at times causing them emotional distress. The vocabulary used by the pupils to express these emotions included

stressed, sad and angry. In speaking of their emotional experiences of school, access to the sensory room is seen as a key advantage of attending the autism classes. When asked what kind of things he can do in the sensory room, Andrew (3rd class) responded “relax”.

Stress was also an emotion pupils related to. Brendan attributed his placement in the autism class to his stress levels, claiming “the main only reason I’m in it is.....And then I normally always got stressed that’s why I was in here” (Bendan, 3rd class). In a string of explanations, Brian admits, “I used to throw chairs and I once flipped over a desk”, “I threw a chair at a teacher” explaining “I used to be always overwhelmed” (Brian, 2nd class). Looking at the progress he has made with the intervention of the autism class, Brian realises “I used to be really...I used to be I used to say no to everything”. Brian’s responses show that his behaviour was communicating that his mainstream class environment (physical, social or cultural) was not working for him. The deficit was in the environment and when the environment better matched his strengths, overwhelming stress and behavioural difficulties were no longer an issue.

Some coping resources were shared by Dawn (2nd class) and Deirdre (3rd class) who shared their use of fidgets, poppits and bubble wrap (see below). Ben and Brian also explained that in their school they had a calm down box to help them calm down before attempting work after break times. Denis spoke of his reintegration into mainstream following the Covid 19 pandemic. “At the first time I was like...like am worried about it that I would be in there for the rest of the year and that I wouldn’t go back to here (autism class)” (Denis, 3rd class).

Image 3. Dawn's fidgets pictures taken during photovoice session

It is clear that the pupils were in tune with their emotions and in many cases they showed an understanding of unacceptable behaviour in school when frustration or stress crept in. The autism class was seen as a safe haven where they could retreat to in times of adversity.

Theme Three: Adult perspectives

Adult participants indicated that five pupils were aware that they were autistic, or different in some respect. This was demonstrated by masking behaviours. For example, Ms Derrane (autism class teacher) shared her experience of Dawn (2nd class) demonstrating masking behaviours when in the mainstream classroom;

“I would say she understands that she needs a bit of extra help with me. She knows that I give her a break and she will ask for a break more with me and she wouldn't ask for it in the classroom (mainstream) like and even if she is ready to explode she wouldn't ask for it. So we have to kind of watch that a bit...but am I would say there is a bit of understanding but it's not really clear”.

While this was unclear to Ms Derrane, there is a certain amount of strain being observed when in the mainstream classroom and this would appear to be released when Dawn returns to the autism classroom.

Throughout the research the adults spoke of autism in a derogatory, medical style manner. This was evident particularly when discussing at length the supports which they provided to the pupils to assist them in assimilating to their school environment. Autistic pupils experiencing Social, Emotional and Behavioural Difficulties were highlighted by the adults in this research, who noted that there was a limit to the masking capacities of some of the children who would “explode” once they returned to the autism special class after time spent in the mainstream. Anxiety was highlighted as a main struggle for the pupils from the adults' perspectives, and this was eased by limiting the exposure of autistic pupils to the mainstream for extended periods of time.

Limitations

As the autistic community are a heterogenous group, the findings from this research in which fifteen autistic pupils participated are not generalisable. Additionally, the absence of more widespread parent and indeed mainstream teacher participation made the triangulation of data a difficult task.

The presence of just one researcher limited the reach of this research with more widespread research with autistic pupils recommended to ascertain broader experiences of this group of pupils.

Only qualitative data was collected as the research was pitched towards the strengths of autistic pupils aged from 4-12 based on findings of a systematic literature review carried out on research with autistic children between 2004 and 2020.

No non-verbal participants involved in this research. This was perhaps by consequence of parents or indeed school management/teachers involved in the selection favouring verbal participants or seeing them as more able to participate in the research.

Two of the participating four schools were not facilitating the inclusion of autistic pupils in their mainstream classes as well as their autism special classes during data collection. As a result of covid-19 guidelines both of these schools had only allowed segregated provision for the previous 15 months prior to data collection. This had an effect on the pupils' ability to remember their lived experience of being in their mainstream classes.

Conclusions

It is clear that the autistic pupils are experiencing social emotional and behavioural challenges at much higher levels in the mainstream setting versus the autism setting because their autism is more likely accepted in the autism class and the pressure to mask and conform to neurotypical expectations is lessened in that environment. This echoes Goodall's (2020) findings with regards to inclusion being a feeling and not a place. Hence, the autism class is experienced as a more accommodating setting for autistic pupils than their mainstream classes.

Throughout the findings the adults persistently showed a deficit view of autism in many of their responses. These views held by adults are undoubtedly influencing some of the children's self-perception as indicated by their responses where they considered their behaviours and emotions to be inappropriate. The adult focus appears to be on exposing the autistic children to neurotypical settings, in order to allow them to learn neurotypical ways of socialising and managing their emotions. It is important that autistic pupils are not feeling pressurised by the school environment to change their neurodiverse tendencies. The neurotypical mainstream classroom must adjust in order to protect the well-being of autistic pupils.

There is a clear tension between pupil and adult voices throughout this research. It is important to acknowledge the wealth of knowledge gained from engaging the voices of the autistic pupils and only from doing this can the common practice of adults advocating on behalf of pupils be truly seen as being insufficient. Therefore greater trust is needed in empowering children to act as co-researchers in matters which affect them.

Key implications for policy, practice and research were discovered in this research. Firstly, if inclusion is to become a real possibility, it is vital for adults to be made more aware of their innately deficit perceptions of autism. This requires urgent attention from the policy makers nationwide. Secondly, in terms of practice, it is important that there is more of a concerted effort in developing whole-school awareness of neurodiverse and neurotypical representation in matters of planning, consultation and inclusion. Finally, there is a great dearth of research in this area. There is a great need for more research to be carried out with autistic pupils to voice and share their experiences of schooling in order to develop a system which is fit for purpose.

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Appendix 1.

Duncan's (2013) 4-SASA

Outline of Agnieszka Duncan's 4-SASA
Step 1: Identifying signs within drawings through manual annotations using transcriptions of the child's conversation and description of representations to ensure the child's meaning is privileged
Step 2: Isolating individual signs which were identified in step 1 and documenting the child's understanding of signs and social significance (in social semiotic terms: embedding the signs in the social)
Step 3: Organising signs using specific categories of social semiotic analysis (mode, size, colour, salience) and identifying the child's motivation and interest for specific sign production
Step 4: Synthesis of the child's perspectives from steps 1-3 focusing on information relating to the experiences of <i>autistic pupils and their inclusion in the primary school setting through dual provision</i> . In summary this stage is concerned with constructing a summary of the child's experiences and perspectives of dual provision.
Collation of step 4 outcomes (summary of the child's perspectives on their experience of dual provision) from every drawing (of the same child) to produce a rich account of the child's perspectives on dual provision